

Effect of stopping hydroelectric power generation on the dynamics of electricity prices: An event study approach

Stephanía Mosquera-López^{a,*}, Jorge M. Uribe^{b,c}, Diego F. Manotas-Duque^a,

^aSchool of Industrial Engineering, Universidad del Valle, Calle 13 # 100-00, Cali, Colombia.

^bRiskcenter-University of Barcelona, Av. Diagonal, 690 08034, Barcelona, Spain.

^cDepartment of Economics, Universidad del Valle, Calle 13 # 100-00, Cali, Colombia.

*Corresponding author. Phone number: +57 321 21 00, Ext: 7006. E-mail:

stephania.mosquera.lopez@correounivalle.edu.co

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Abstract

Supply shocks in electricity markets that disrupt energy production cause unexpected spikes in prices, which in turn have economic consequences, such as higher risk and therefore higher costs and losses for producers and consumers of electricity. One relevant shock in this sector is the halting of hydroelectric power generation due to the freezing of water reservoirs after the temperature drops below zero degrees Celsius, and therefore less efficient technologies such as thermal plants must begin to produce electricity. Using an event study approach, this shock in the Nord Pool market is explicitly identified, and the economic importance of expanding the interconnected market and the inclusion of more renewable sources in the generation mix of the system to smooth out price spikes is quantified. When a freezing event occurs, it is found that the average electricity prices increase (between €1 and €6), and that the negative relationship between temperature and prices also increases (for each degree that the temperature decreases, prices increase between €1 and €3). However, as expected, these changes are more pronounced in countries that are most dependent on hydropower generation. By identifying this supply shock, relevant insights are presented for market players, such as policy makers, investors, and consumers and producers, whose decisions are influenced by the effect of temperature, particularly when it causes the stopping of hydroelectric plants.

Keywords: electricity prices; hydropower; weather; event study; threshold regression.

1. Introduction

Supply shocks in electricity markets that disrupt energy production cause unexpected spikes in the price of electricity. In a market where the electricity generation mix relies mainly on hydroelectric generation, as is the case in the Nord Pool market, supply shocks that negatively affect their production cause the necessity for more expensive technologies, such as thermal plants, to produce electricity to meet demand, and therefore generate unexpected price increases. These price spikes have fundamental economic consequences for producers and consumers of electricity. For instance, unexpected price spikes imply higher risk for market players: more volatile cash flows result in higher costs, and hence in higher losses.

The supply shocks that disrupt electricity production are often caused by weather factors as the role of weather in electricity price formation is indisputable. Water reservoirs depend on the level of precipitation; wind power generation relies on wind speed; temperature affects the demand for electricity as well as its supply. In the specific case of temperature, when the temperature drops below zero degrees Celsius, water reservoirs freeze and hydroelectric plants are not able to use water any more to continue generating power.

When hydroelectric plants stop generating power, thermal plants must be turned on, increasing the price of electricity, unless the market counts on other renewable sources, such as wind power or solar generation to meet demand. Moreover, this shock may be transmitted to different areas from the area where the plant operates. Thus, identifying the supply shock derived from the freezing of water reservoirs allows one to quantify the economic importance of expanding the interconnected market of Nord Pool, the inclusion of more renewable sources in the generation mix of the system and viable storage. Hence, one effect of renewable sources is the smoothing of price spikes.

The objective of this study is to identify this supply shock: the effect of the freezing of water reservoirs when temperature drops below zero degrees in the Nord Pool market on the dynamics of electricity prices. This market has different areas of transactions and countries, which allows us to compare among them to relate the effects of the shock to the generation mix. Although it is straightforward that the dependence upon hydric sources is

the main source of unexpected price spikes, we quantify this dependence in Euros, and therefore we show the incentives to diversify the generation mix.

Not only this supply shock is identified, but also a contribution to understanding the nonlinearities that determine electricity prices is made. While previous studies have found that the relationship between weather and prices is nonlinear [1], this study shows that nonlinearity is caused by the freezing of water reservoirs, which is a novelty in the literature. Therefore, it is possible to create hedging strategies that allow the management of very cold days in a more appropriate manner and the smoothing of this shock through other renewable generation sources.

Previous studies in the literature have used weather factors to model or forecast electricity prices and demand (see [1,2,11–19,3–10] and Section 2 for an extended literature review). However, none of these studies isolates the effect of stopping hydroelectric plants due to water freezing, as is done here. In this study, an event study approach is followed to explicitly identify the change in the relationship between prices and temperature once hydroelectric plants stop generating power and less efficient technologies, such as thermal plants, must begin to produce electricity. The effect of this supply shock on the dynamics of electricity prices is assessed by means of regressions with indicator variables and threshold regressions that endogenously capture nonlinearities related to price formation in electricity markets.

The days when the temperature drops below zero degrees are considered as the event of interest. The event study methodology has been used extensively in economic and financial literature since its introduction by [20] to examine the effect of certain events on the dynamics of stock prices. Nevertheless, in the energy literature, very few event studies have been conducted (see a discussion of these in the next Section).

Using data from the Nord Pool day-ahead market (Norway, Sweden, Denmark, Finland, and Estonia) to compare the effects across countries that house different power generation mixes, the models proposed are estimated. On the days when the freezing event occurs, that is, when the temperature is zero degrees or less, it is found that the average electricity prices increase and the negative correlation between temperature and prices also increase.

However, as expected, these changes are more pronounced in countries that generate power mainly with hydroelectric plants.

These results provide relevant insights about how a higher dependence on hydroelectric production makes an area/country more vulnerable to temperature, particularly when it drops below zero, and other more expensive technologies, such as thermal plants, must be turned on to meet demand. Nevertheless, the integrated market becomes vulnerable to this supply shock as it may be transmitted to other areas.

By explicitly identifying the supply shock of stopping hydroelectric generation on each area of the Nord Pool, relevant insights for market players are given: policy makers interested in expanding the market or increasing its transmission capacities; investors seeking to invest in other renewable power generation sources different from hydroelectric plants; consumers and producers forecasting increment in prices due to freezing events for planning their buying/selling strategies.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. The literature review is presented in Section 2. In section 3, the data used in the analysis is presented. Section 4 contains the methodology. In section 5, the main results are presented, and in section 6, they are discussed. Finally, in section 7, the conclusions are presented.

2. Literature Review

Weather factors are crucial in the formation of electricity prices as they affect demand and supply. For instance, through demand, lower temperatures trigger a higher consumption of electricity and vice versa. Hence for example, higher temperatures imply lower heating requirements, which translates into lower prices. Owing to supply, temperature affects prices through the freezing of hydro reservoirs, disabling the generation of power with hydroelectric plants, which is the supply shock identified here. Wind speed determines wind power generation and precipitation is expected to affect the level of hydro reservoirs.

Following the financial literature on asset pricing, portfolios or single assets can be priced in absolute terms, taking reference of their exposure to fundamental sources of risk (risk factors), generally of macroeconomic nature [21]. In the case of electricity markets, weather factors are fundamentals sources of risk, which determine the dynamics of supply

and demand. Therefore, resorting to weather variables that directly reflect the electricity supply and demand side was opted, instead of hydropower and wind power generation series.

This approach also has been followed by a branch of the literature that uses weather factors to explain the dynamics of (or to forecast) electricity demand and prices. Table 1 presents a summary of the literature review. It shows the reference of the study, the analyzed market, weather variables employed in each case, and if the study analyzes the effect of weather on electricity demand or prices. In the case of electricity demand, the seminal studies that assess the relationship between temperature and demand in the United States date back to [2,3]. More recently, [4] forecast daily electricity load with cooling and heating-degree days in Spain. [5] find that for the California Independent System Operators (ISO) in the United States, load and prices are sensitive to temperature. [6] analyze the impact of mean daily air temperature in the consumption of electricity in Serbia. [7,8] study the impact of temperature on sectorial electricity demand in Spain and Korea, respectively. [9] assess the effect of climate change on the consumption and price of electricity in Massachusetts, United States. Authors such as [10–14], in addition to evaluating the impact of temperature on electricity demand, also consider variables such as wind speed, precipitation, solar irradiation, and humidity.

Turning the attention to the branch of the literature that models and forecasts electricity prices using weather variables, [15] quantify the effect of heat waves on German electricity market, specifically on market prices, production costs, and consumer and producer surpluses. Furthermore, for Germany, [16] model the European Energy Exchange (EEX) price with temperature as a proxy for electricity demand. [17] determine day-ahead Italian electricity prices using hourly temperature variables. For the Nord Pool, authors such as [1,18,19] employ temperature in addition to other weather factors, such as wind speed, precipitation, and solar irradiation, aiming to explain the dynamics of electricity prices, or to forecast them. In this set of studies, nonlinearities in prices are addressed only by [1].

Table 1. Literature Review Summary

Reference	Market	Weather Variables					Effect on		
		Temp	Wind	Preci	Irrad	Other	Demand	Prices	Other
[2]	United States	*					*		
[3]	United States	*					*		
[4]	Spain	*					*		
[5]	California ISO	*					*	*	
[10]	Abu Dhabi	*	*		*	*	*		
[6]	Serbia	*					*		
[7]	Spain	*					*		
[8]	Korea	*					*		
[11]	Canada	*				*	*		
[12]	South Korea	*	*	*	*	*	*		
[9]	Massachusetts	*					*	*	
[13]	Great Britain	*	*		*		*		*
[14]	United States	*	*			*	*		
[18]	Nord Pool	*		*				*	
[19]	NO – DK	**	*	*				*	
[15]	Germany	*						*	*
[16]	EEX	*						*	
[1]	Nord Pool	*	*	*	*			*	
[17]	Italy	*						*	

NO stands for Norway, DK for Denmark, BE for Belgium, FR for France, DE for Germany, and NL for the Netherlands. EEX stands for European Energy Exchange (Germany). The acronym ISO is Independent System Operators. Temp stands for temperature, Wind for wind speed, Preci for precipitation, and Irrad for solar irradiance.

Regarding nonlinearities of electricity prices, the literature has extensively documented them using a variety of methods, such as switching regressions, quantile regressions, neural networks, and machine learning techniques (e.g., [1,22–36]). Finally, event studies in the energy literature are rather scarce. Authors such as [37–40] examine the effect of mergers and acquisitions of firms/utilities in the energy sector on enterprise value. [41] analyze the impact of announcements of acquisition of oil and gas reserves on United States stock prices in the sector. [42] assess the impact of environmental regulation on stock prices of Chinese fossil-based energy companies.

This study adds to the aforementioned literature by adopting an event study approach to assess the nonlinear effects of temperature on water reservoirs after a freezing event has occurred. The empirical strategy used here is based on threshold regression that allows addressing the nonlinear dynamics of electricity prices and electricity seasonalities in a direct manner.

3. Data description and preliminary analysis

The Nord Pool is the leading power market in Europe and one of the biggest integrated markets worldwide. In the day-ahead market (Elsport), producers and consumers make their bids for the delivery of electricity for each hour of the next day. The markets that are part of the Nord Pool are divided into different bidding areas (currently, there are 15 sub-areas, in addition to the total area). The pricing mechanism functions as follows: first, the system establishes the prices for each hour of the following day that balances the aggregate supply and aggregate demand; second, according to transmission capacity and congestion, different area prices may be established to solve bottlenecks. Table 2 displays the Nordic power generation mix in 2016. Norway and Sweden are the countries that are most dependent on hydroelectric generation, while Denmark relies fundamentally on wind power and fossil fuels generation. Finland has a more diversified generation mix, depending mostly on nuclear power and fossil fuels generation. Lastly, Estonia relies fundamentally on fossil fuels for its generation of electricity.

Table 2. Nordic power generation mix 2016 (%)

Energy Source	Sweden	Finland	Denmark	Norway	Estonia
Fossil Fuels	3%	27%	39%	2%	85%
Nuclear Power	43%	31%	0%	0%	0%
Hydropower	30%	16%	0%	96%	0%
Wind Power	16%	8%	45%	2%	9%
Other Renewable	8%	17%	16%	0%	7%

Source: ENTSO-E.

The dataset of the dependent variables consists of the day-ahead electricity prices (see Figure 1) quoted in EUR/MWh for the 13 of the 16 bidding areas (see Table 3) in the Nord Pool market¹.

Table 3. Bidding areas and acronyms

Area	Description	Area	Description
SE1	Luleå	NO1	Oslo
SE2	Sundsvall	NO2	Kristiansand
SE3	Stockholm	NO3	Molde, Trondheim
SE4	Malmö	NO4	Tromsø
FI	Finland	NO5	Bergen
DK1	Western Denmark	EE	Estonia
DK2	Eastern Denmark		

The dataset of the explanatory variables consists of temperature, wind speed, and precipitation for Sweden, Finland, Denmark, Norway, and Estonia, and consumption of the 13 bidding areas, natural gas price, and coal price (see Figure 1). These variables are included in the model lagged, as in [26]. The reason is that the bids that market participants make today determine the price of tomorrow; thus, the price in $t+1$ is set with the information up to t . The frequency of the data is daily, and due to data availability, the sample period starts on January 1, 2013, and ends on December 31, 2016. The electricity prices and consumption were obtained from the Nord Pool Spot, and the other explanatory variables were obtained from Bloomberg and Datastream.

As shown in Figure 1, the independent variables are divided into freezing events and control variables. The freezing events' variables are temperature, which is an average of the actual temperature of the main cities within each country of the Nord Pool, and an indicator variable that takes the value of one when the temperature of the country is below zero

¹ The System Price is excluded as analyzing the effect of temperature when it decreases below zero degrees on the prices is the aim of this study, but the temperature is associated with each country of the Nord Pool, and not with the full area. The prices of Latvia and Lithuania are also excluded as they present limitations on the transmission capacity within the Nord Pool, thus the results may be misleading.

degrees, and a value of zero otherwise. The control variables are expected to also affect electricity prices, and the models should include them. Wind speed and precipitation are control variables that are also related to weather, such as the freezing event variables, and are constructed as the average of the actual wind speed/precipitation of the main cities within each country. The other control variables are market-related as they affect the prices through demand or supply of electricity, and are: consumption, which is equal to the total megawatts hours consumed per area of the Nord Pool; natural gas prices from the GASPOOL index; and coal prices from the API2 index (see Appendix 1 for a complete summary and description of the independent variables used).

Table 4 presents the descriptive statistics for 5 of the 13 area prices analyzed, and Figure 2 depicts the behavior of these prices during the data span. We focus our analysis on one area price in the countries that have more than one bidding area (Sweden, Denmark, and Norway). Sweden and Norway, which are responsible for 73% of Nordic power generation, exhibit similar patterns: lower average prices and matching spikes.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics of the electricity prices (EUR/MWh): January 2013–December 2016

	SE1	FI	DK1	NO1	EE
Mean	30.18	34.82	29.80	27.73	36.23
Median	30.23	34.71	29.27	27.17	35.40
Maximum	88.10	94.78	436.33	86.39	124.77
Minimum	3.51	6.30	-6.28	3.65	6.30
Std. Dev.	9.53	8.99	14.49	9.36	9.63
Skewness	0.22	0.69	15.13	0.38	1.52
Kurtosis	4.33	7.39	425.80	4.17	12.16
Observations	1461	1461	1461	1461	1461

Figure 2 plots the average temperature of each country in the sample and Table 5 displays its descriptive statistics. Finland registers the highest number of times of events when the temperature drops below zero degrees Celsius (24%), while Denmark presents a lesser number of events (6%).

Table 5. Descriptive statistics of temperature (degrees Celsius): January 2013–December 2016

Country	Average	Maximum	Minimum	No. Times Temp $\leq 0^\circ$	% Temp $\leq 0^\circ$
Sweden	5.45	21.58	-14.94	351	24%
Finland	4.32	22.78	-26.26	462	32%
Denmark	9.29	22.16	-6.27	83	6%
Norway	5.23	18.64	-9.91	286	20%
Estonia	7.14	24.75	-19.11	266	18%

Regarding the stationarity of the data, in Table 6, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for all the variables is presented. All the 13 area prices are stationary, while all the consumption series present a stochastic trend. The temperature, wind speed, and precipitation series for each country are stationary. Finally, natural gas and coal prices indices present a stochastic trend.

Table 6. ADF test

	SE1	SE2	SE3	SE4	FI	DK1	DK2
Price, t-ADF	-3.297**	-3.299**	-3.616***	-3.725***	-3.929***	-7.787***	-4.347***
Temperature, t-ADF	-2.475**	-2.475**	-2.475**	-2.475**	-3.197***	-2.838*	-2.838*
Wind Speed, t-ADF	-14.533***	-14.533***	-14.533***	-14.533***	-19.276***	-18.578***	-18.578***
Precipitation, t-ADF	-6.230***	-6.230***	-6.230***	-6.230***	-3.742***	-5.705***	-5.705***
Consumption, t-ADF	-1.064	-0.712	-1.058	-1.019	-0.634	-0.871	-0.856
GASPOOL, t-ADF	-2.758	-2.758	-2.758	-2.758	-2.758	-2.758	-2.758
API2, t-ADF	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115
	NO1	NO2	NO3	NO4	NO5	EE	
Price, t-ADF	-3.455***	-3.094**	-3.278**	-3.059**	-3.070**	-6.227***	
Temperature, t-ADF	-2.518**	-2.518**	-2.518**	-2.518**	-2.518**	-2.541**	
Wind Speed, t-ADF	-12.226***	-12.226***	-12.226***	-12.226***	-12.226***	-19.622***	
Precipitation, t-ADF	-3.018***	-3.018***	-3.018***	-3.018***	-3.018***	-7.478***	
Consumption, t-ADF	-1.238	-0.960	-0.369	-0.486	-0.733	-0.836	
GASPOOL, t-ADF	-2.758	-2.758	-2.758	-2.758	-2.758	-2.758	
API2, t-ADF	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115	-0.115	

*, **, and *** indicate that the null hypothesis is rejected and stationarity at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels is found. The variables temperature, wind speed, and precipitation are measured for each country and not for each area of transaction, therefore the t-ADF presented is equal for each area of the same country. In the case of Consumption, GASPOOL, and API2 that house a stochastic trend, the series were transformed by computing differences of the logarithms (log-returns). Additionally, for GASPOOL and API2, the t-ADF displayed for each area price is the same across all areas.

4. Methodology

Identifying the effect of stopping hydroelectric plants on electricity prices in the Nord Pool by means of an event study approach is proposed (see Figure 4). First, a model with an indicator variable that takes the value one (1) if the temperature is below zero, and zero (0) otherwise is used. Zero degrees was selected a priori as the threshold of temperature at which hydroelectric plants are no longer able to turbine water due to the freezing of water reservoirs. This model allows the identification of how much the average electricity price changes (increases or decreases) and how much the correlation between temperature and prices changes once a freezing event occurs (see Section 4.1).

Nevertheless, the threshold at which a freezing event occurs will not necessarily be zero degrees for the following reasons: (i) the variable temperature used is an average of the temperatures of the main cities in each country and not the actual temperature of the area; and (ii) other physical conditions, such as the snowpack level, can alter the level at which the water reservoirs actually freeze or unfreeze. Therefore, a second model that uses threshold regression for endogenously selecting the threshold value at which the relationship between temperature and prices shifts is proposed (see Section 4.2).

4.1. Regressions with indicator variable

Defining an indicator variable that takes the value of 0 for days when the temperature of the area/country is higher than zero degrees Celsius and a value of 1 otherwise

$$I_{it} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } temp_{it} > 0^\circ \\ 1 & \text{if } temp_{it} \leq 0^\circ \end{cases}, \quad (1)$$

where subscript i denotes the bidding area and t a date.

The first model assumes that price is given by an intercept, the indicator variable I_{it} , temperature, and the interaction effect between I_{it} and temperature, and is as follows:

$$price_{it} = \beta_{oi} + \beta_{1i}I_{it} + \beta_{2i}temp_{it} + \beta_{3i}I_{it}temp_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (2)$$

where $temp_{it}$ is the temperature measured in degrees Celsius.

In this case, after a freezing event occurs (i.e., when $I_{it} = 1$), the regression intercept shifts from β_{oi} to $\beta_{oi} + \beta_{1i}$. If $\beta_{1i} > 0$, the event increases the average price, while if $\beta_{1i} < 0$, the event increases the average price of electricity. However, a freezing event may also cause a change in the (partial) correlation between temperature and prices. In other words, a freezing event may change the slope of the regression. This change is measured in the model by a slope shift β_{2i} to $\beta_{2i} + \beta_{3i}$. Once again, the change may be a reduction or an increment in the correlation.

An extended model is shown in equation 3. The original version has been augmented with control variables that help to explain electricity price dynamics² as follows:

$$price_{it} = \beta_{oi} + \beta_{1i}I_{it-1} + \beta_{2i}temp_{it-1} + \beta_{3i}I_{it}temp_{it-1} + \beta_{4i}wind_{it-1} + \beta_{5i}precip_{it-1} + \beta_{6i}consum_{it-1} + \beta_{7i}gas_{t-1} + \beta_{8i}coal_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (3)$$

where $wind_{it-1}$ is the wind speed measured in m/s; $precip_{it-1}$ is the precipitation measured as an integer in 0.01 mm; $consum_{it-1}$ is the consumption of electricity per area; gas is the GASPOOL index; and coal is the API2 index (see Table 1)³.

4.2. Threshold regression

Threshold regressions are nonlinear models that allow to empirically model two (or more) regimes in the regression specification. In other words, within these models, the correlation between the explanatory and explained variables is allowed to differ before and after a certain threshold is trespassed in the data. In this case, such a threshold is related to

² The results presented here are robust to the inclusion of a variable that measures export and import flows between the transaction areas in the Nord Pool constructed as $trade_{t,i} = \sum_{j=1}^N exports_{j,i} - \sum_{j=1}^N imports_{j,i}$ following [46], where $exports_{j,i}$ is the total amount of electricity exports from area i to area j , $imports_{j,i}$ is the total amount of electricity imports of area i from area j , and N is the total number of areas, excluding area i . Indeed, this variable lacks any explanatory power on prices, once the fundamental weather variables have been considered.

³ In order to take into account the possible multicollinearity problems in the model, specifically between Temperature and Consumption, the Pearson correlation coefficient among these two variables was estimated and is presented in Appendix 1. For none of the 13 areas of the Nord Pool, the Pearson correlation coefficient between Temperature and Consumption is higher than -0.05.

temperature. This relationship is important as the empirical measure of temperature for each country is an average of the actual temperature in its main cities. Thus, the threshold at which hydroelectric plants are no longer able to generate power is not necessarily exactly zero degrees Celsius.

More specifically, a threshold regression model combines a linear specification with a regime switching structure to describe a nonlinear relationship between the variables, as explained in [43–45]. The change in the regime occurs when an observed variable crosses unknown threshold values.

Suppose a multiple linear regression model with T observations and m potential thresholds, which gives $m + 1$ potential regimes

$$price_{it} = X'_{it-1}\beta_i + temp_{it-1}\alpha_{ij} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (4)$$

where the subscript i denotes the bidding area, t a day, j a regime, and $j = 0 \dots m$.

Temperature is the observable threshold variable and X_{it} is a vector that contains all the other variables that are not regime-specific, that is, wind speed, precipitation, consumption, natural gas prices, and coal prices.

The thresholds allowed by the model are $\gamma_1 < \gamma_2 < \dots < \gamma_m$ so that the model is in regime j if $\gamma_j \leq temp_{it-1} < \gamma_{j+1}$.

In a two-regime model (i.e., temperature has a single threshold), the model is given by

$$price_{it} = \begin{cases} X'_{it-1}\beta_i + temp_{it-1}\alpha_{i1} + \varepsilon_{it} & \text{if } -\infty < temp_{it-1} < \gamma_1 \\ X'_{it-1}\beta_i + temp_{it-1}\alpha_{i2} + \varepsilon_{it} & \text{if } \gamma_1 \leq temp_{it-1} < \infty \end{cases}, \quad (5)$$

allowing for $m + 1$ individual regimes, we have that

$$price_{it} = X'_{it-1}\beta_i + \sum_{j=0}^m 1_j(temp_{it-1}, \gamma) \cdot temp_{it-1}\alpha_{ij} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (6)$$

where $1_j(temp_{it}, \gamma)$ is an indicator function equal to $1(\gamma_j \leq temp_{it-1} < \gamma_{j+1})$.

5. Results

The models with indicator variables and the threshold models were estimated using Huber-White standard errors. Both models aim to identify whether the relationship between

electricity prices and temperature changes once hydroelectric plants stop generating power, and less efficient technologies, such as thermal plants, begin to produce electricity.

5.1. Regressions with indicator variable

Table 7 presents the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression estimates using indicator variable I_{it} that takes the value of zero when the temperature is above zero degrees, and the value of 1 otherwise. For 8 of 13 area prices, the estimates of the indicator variable effect are significant and positive, showing that the average electricity price increases once $I_{it} = 1$; the average price increases between €2 and €6 once the temperature drops below zero degrees.

When analyzing the slope of the regression before a freezing event occurs (i.e., when the temperature is higher than zero degrees), the relationship between temperature and prices is statistically not significant for most of the area prices (except for FI, NO1, NO2, and NO5). However, after the temperature drops below zero degrees, the temperature has a significant effect on all the area prices. Moreover, this relationship is negative, as expected. The slope changes to approximately -1 and -3, which means that once a freezing event occurs, for each degree that the temperature decreases, prices increase between €1 and €3.

For the area prices of Norway where temperature is significant before the freezing event and has a negative effect, the absolute value of the slope of the regression after $I_{it} = 1$ increases, indicating a higher negative impact of temperature on prices. This result is expected due to the generation mix of Norway (see Table 2), where 96% of the power generation is met with hydroelectric plants.

Figure 5 plots the relationship between temperature and prices, before and after the temperature is equal to zero degrees. For all the cases, the intercept shifts upwards after the temperature drops below zero degrees. Denmark and Estonia exhibit the biggest change in their intercepts, which indicates that after a freezing event occurs, the increment of the average price is higher in comparison to the other areas.

Table 7. Regression with an indicator variable of the freezing level

	SE1	SE2	SE3	SE4	FI	DK1	DK2
Intercept	28.281***	28.283***	28.583***	29.272***	32.077***	28.974***	31.065***

	(0.425)	(0.425)	(0.431)	(0.452)	(0.461)	(0.571)	(0.571)
I-Freezing	1.791**	1.789**	1.569*	1.724*	0.623	5.006**	2.723
	(0.851)	(0.851)	(0.859)	(0.909)	(0.776)	(2.115)	(2.473)
Temperature	0.073	0.073	0.069	0.046	0.190***	0.040	-0.013
	(0.047)	(0.047)	(0.047)	(0.048)	(0.044)	(0.062)	(0.049)
I*Temperature	-1.035***	-1.035***	-1.199***	-1.094***	-0.951***	-1.563*	-2.783**
	(0.165)	(0.165)	(0.165)	(0.169)	(0.111)	(0.893)	(1.205)
	NO1	NO2	NO3	NO4	NO5	EE	
Intercept	28.281***	27.851***	28.997***	27.957***	28.080***	32.649***	
	(0.384)	(0.367)	(0.395)	(0.374)	(0.373)	(0.427)	
I-Freezing	1.139	1.986**	1.388	0.936	2.053**	5.732***	
	(1.015)	(0.963)	(1.046)	(0.961)	(0.999)	(0.889)	
Temperature	-0.331***	-0.296***	-0.018	-0.053	-0.340***	0.276***	
	(0.048)	(0.046)	(0.049)	(0.049)	(0.047)	(0.045)	
I*Temperature	-1.575***	-1.138***	-1.553***	-1.677***	-1.058***	-0.629***	
	(0.285)	(0.251)	(0.292)	(0.282)	(0.263)	(0.136)	

*, **, and *** indicate significance at a 90%, 95%, and 99% confidence level, respectively. I-Freezing is an indicator variable that takes the value of 1 if the temperature is below zero degrees Celsius and the value of 0 otherwise. The standard deviation of each regression is presented in parentheses.

For all the areas, except for NO1, the slope of the regression is approximately zero when the temperature is above zero degrees, which shows that for these countries, before a freezing event occurs, the relationship between temperature and electricity prices is almost null. When the temperature is above zero degrees not only do hydroelectric plants generate power, but it is more likely for demand to be lower: higher temperatures imply less dependence on heating devices, therefore the correlation between temperature and prices weakens. Only for Norway, which depends almost completely on hydropower generation, the relation between them is always negative and significant.

A change in the slope of the model that describes each area-price is documented for all the markets considered. In other words, even though not all areas are highly dependent on hydroelectric power generation, once a freezing event occurs, all of them are affected by the increment in the (negative) relationship between temperature and prices. This is a result of the transmission between areas, mainly of shocks from Norway and Sweden, which are

the biggest participants in the market. Naturally, the most dependent on hydropower generation areas exhibit the steepest slopes when the temperature is below zero degrees.

In Table 8 and Figure 6, the results of a regression with an indicator variable of the freezing level augmented with control variables are presented. The control variables include wind speed and precipitation. High levels of wind speed are expected to reduce electricity prices as wind power is one of the cheapest power sources. Following the latter reasoning, it is expected for higher precipitation levels to reduce electricity prices and vice versa, thus precipitation is considered as a *proxy* for water reservoirs. The other control variables are market-related factors: consumption, natural gas price, and coal price. Consumption is a *proxy* for electricity demand. Natural gas and coal are input factors in the generation of electricity, and hence are expected to affect electricity price dynamics via supply.

The effect of wind speed on prices is significant and negative for all area prices, as expected, indicating that higher levels of wind speed are related to lower prices.

Precipitation is only statistically not significant for all the areas within Sweden and Norway, but for the other countries the estimates are approximately equal to zero.

Consumption has a significant and positive effect on prices. Natural gas is significant with the expected positive effect on prices for all the countries, except for Norway, which only generates 2% of its total electricity from fossil fuels. Coal prices have the expected positive effect on prices, but it is not significant across all the areas.

Comparing the results in Table 8 with the results in Table 7, it is found that the estimated coefficient of the joint effect of the indicator variable and temperature (i.e., β_{3i}) is smaller than the coefficient of the regression without control variables. Nevertheless, the sign of the effect of the freezing events and temperature is maintained, which means that independent of whether the model includes control variables or not, freezing events always affect electricity prices in the same manner.

Table 8. Regression with an indicator variable of the freezing level with control variables**(a)**

	SE1	SE2	SE3	SE4	FI	DK1	DK2
Intercept	32.078*** (1.045)	32.480*** (1.049)	32.673*** (1.046)	32.984*** (1.059)	34.691*** (0.979)	34.511*** (1.263)	34.929*** (1.058)
I-Freezing	1.435* (0.855)	1.440* (0.850)	1.143 (0.852)	1.457 (0.896)	0.385 (0.766)	3.366 (2.250)	1.565 (2.546)
Temperature	0.011 (0.050)	0.005 (0.050)	0.003 (0.049)	-0.011 (0.050)	0.152*** (0.045)	-0.034 (0.057)	-0.070 (0.050)
I*Temperature	-0.920*** (0.164)	-0.891*** (0.163)	-1.044*** (0.163)	-0.943*** (0.166)	-0.812*** (0.110)	-1.506 (0.933)	-2.765** (1.232)
<i>Control Variables</i>							
Wind Speed	-0.446*** (0.115)	-0.501*** (0.115)	-0.471*** (0.114)	-0.415*** (0.116)	-0.234** (0.106)	-0.361*** (0.087)	-0.268*** (0.072)
Precipitation	0.000 (0.002)	0.000 (0.002)	-0.001 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.004*** (0.002)	-0.007*** (0.002)	-0.003* (0.002)
Consumption	14.134*** (4.324)	19.862*** (3.914)	25.527*** (3.495)	20.516*** (2.639)	40.117*** (3.943)	25.884*** (4.149)	32.035*** (3.796)
GASPOOL	3.038** (1.442)	2.297 (1.463)	3.051** (1.402)	3.514** (1.447)	4.834*** (1.597)	12.537*** (1.592)	10.365*** (1.879)
API2	23.922 (20.122)	23.788 (20.408)	24.480 (19.980)	28.467 (20.393)	10.489 (19.550)	8.977 (21.899)	14.962 (20.181)

(b)

	NO1	NO2	NO3	NO4	NO5	EE
Intercept	32.092*** (1.185)	31.256*** (1.139)	34.716*** (1.199)	31.566*** (1.159)	31.733*** (1.154)	40.387*** (1.215)
I-Freezing	0.844 (1.002)	1.731* (0.949)	1.016 (1.031)	0.607 (0.957)	1.771* (0.984)	4.254*** (0.840)
Temperature	-0.422*** (0.055)	-0.376*** (0.054)	-0.153*** (0.057)	-0.138*** (0.056)	-0.426*** (0.055)	0.150*** (0.047)
I*Temperature	-1.371*** (0.289)	-0.955*** (0.258)	-1.242*** (0.297)	-1.485*** (0.284)	-0.868*** (0.271)	-0.557*** (0.126)
<i>Control Variables</i>						
Wind Speed	-0.300*** (0.108)	-0.263** (0.104)	-0.446*** (0.108)	-0.267** (0.105)	-0.279*** (0.105)	-0.649*** (0.100)
Precipitation	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.002** (0.001)
Consumption	6.506** (3.159)	7.978* (4.774)	16.971*** (5.221)	17.622*** (5.427)	7.056 (4.978)	24.536*** (3.071)
GASPOOL	1.860	1.468	1.807	1.751	1.481	5.033**

	(2.468)	(2.287)	(1.650)	(1.744)	(2.384)	(2.191)
API2	16.796	13.743	28.946	14.608	9.893	5.580
	(15.829)	(14.461)	(17.783)	(14.957)	(15.008)	(19.135)

*, **, and *** indicate significance at a 90%, 95%, and 99% confidence level, respectively. I-Freezing is an indicator variable that takes the value of 1 if the temperature is below zero degrees Celsius and the value of 0 otherwise. The standard deviation of each regression is presented in parentheses.

5.2. Threshold Regression

Table 9 presents the results of the threshold regression that endogenously chooses the temperature level(s) at which the relationship between prices and temperature changes. For the four areas in Sweden (SE1, SE2, SE3, and SE4) presented in Table 9(a), the temperature has one threshold at 1.97° Celsius, and therefore two regimes. When the temperature is below 1.97°, the relationship between temperature and prices is negative and significant. In this regime, for each degree that the temperature drops, the price increases by approximately €1. When the temperature is above or equal to 1.97°, the effect of the temperature on prices is negative, but not significant. Once again, similar to the results of Section 5.1, the control variables that are significant with the expected sign are wind speed, consumption, and natural gas.

Table 9. Threshold regression with the variable temperature as the threshold variable

	SE1	SE2	SE3	SE4
<i>Threshold Variable</i>				
	TEMP < 1.97 503 obs			
Temperature	-1.022*** (0.111)	-1.002*** (0.110)	-1.119*** (0.110)	-1.068*** (0.110)
	1.97 <= TEMP 956 obs	1.97 <= TEMP 956 obs	1.97 <= TEMP 956 obs	1.97 <= TEMP 956 obs
Temperature	-0.044 (0.044)	-0.049 (0.043)	-0.048 (0.042)	-0.068 (0.043)
<i>Non-Threshold Variables</i>				
Intercept	32.858***	33.252***	33.369***	33.782***

	(0.978)	(0.984)	(0.974)	(0.995)
Wind Speed	-0.460***	-0.515***	-0.480***	-0.429***
	(0.114)	(0.115)	(0.113)	(0.116)
Precipitation	0.000	0.000	-0.001	-0.002
	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.002)
Consumption	14.056***	19.790***	25.508***	20.395***
	(4.320)	(3.919)	(3.489)	(2.639)
GASPOOL	2.607*	1.863	2.747**	3.077**
	(1.413)	(1.436)	(1.365)	(1.410)
API2	22.454	22.317	23.359	26.966
	(20.053)	(20.335)	(19.897)	(20.323)

(b)

	FI	DK1	DK2	EE
<i>Threshold Variable</i>				
	TEMP < - 2.96 284 obs	TEMP < 6.29 501 obs	TEMP < 6.26 499 obs	TEMP < 5.25 665 obs
Temperature	-0.605***	-1.376***	-1.575***	-0.623***
	(0.080)	(0.164)	(0.190)	(0.071)
	-2.96 <= TEMP < 12.27 817 obs	6.29 <= TEMP < 12.90 467 obs	6.26 <= TEMP < 9.17 229 obs	5.25 <= TEMP < 15.90 531 obs
Temperature	-0.159**	-0.622***	-1.043***	-0.156***
	(0.062)	(0.080)	(0.122)	(0.045)
			9.17 <= TEMP < 13.76 315 obs	
Temperature			-0.527***	
			(0.077)	
	12.27 <= TEMP 358 obs	12.90 <= TEMP 491 obs	13.76 <= TEMP 416 obs	15.90 <= TEMP 263 obs
Temperature	0.147***	-0.259***	-0.339***	0.076*
	(0.037)	(0.055)	(0.052)	(0.045)
<i>Non-Threshold Variables</i>				
Intercept	35.622***	38.494***	39.437***	43.358***
	(0.853)	(1.296)	(1.078)	(1.134)
Wind Speed	-0.209**	-0.312***	-0.191***	-0.683***
	(0.103)	(0.082)	(0.069)	(0.100)
Precipitation	-0.005***	-0.006***	-0.003	-0.002***

	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.001)
Consumption	40.134***	25.824***	31.880***	25.118***
	(3.921)	(4.069)	(3.691)	(3.029)
GASPOOL	4.947***	10.681***	8.716***	4.716**
	(1.489)	(1.587)	(1.730)	(2.254)
API2	11.622	2.961	9.621	7.793
	(19.444)	(21.857)	(20.235)	(19.357)

(c)

	NO1	NO2	NO3	NO4	NO5
<i>Threshold Variable</i>					
	TEMP < 1.30 401 obs	TEMP < 1.30 401 obs	TEMP < 1.24 397 obs	TEMP < 1.24 397 obs	TEMP < 11.40 1159 obs
Temperature	-1.831*** (0.185)	-1.529*** (0.162)	-1.517*** (0.183)	-1.663*** (0.178)	-0.931*** (0.058)
	1.30 <= TEMP < 7.35 505 obs	1.30 <= TEMP < 7.35 505 obs			
Temperature	-0.399*** (0.118)	-0.402*** (0.114)			
	7.35 <= TEMP < 11.40 253 obs	7.35 <= TEMP < 11.40 253 obs			
Temperature	-0.770*** (0.078)	-0.742*** (0.077)			
	11.40 <= TEMP 300 obs	11.40 <= TEMP 300 obs	1.24 <= TEMP 1062 obs	1.24 <= TEMP 1062 obs	11.40 <= TEMP 300 obs
Temperature	-0.368*** (0.053)	-0.337*** (0.051)	-0.198*** (0.053)	-0.178*** (0.052)	-0.509*** (0.047)
<i>Non-Threshold Variables</i>					
Intercept	32.753*** (1.163)	32.120*** (1.130)	35.326*** (1.172)	32.122*** (1.122)	34.704*** (1.037)
Wind Speed	-0.298*** (0.106)	-0.262** (0.102)	-0.462*** (0.107)	-0.282*** (0.104)	-0.326*** (0.102)
Precipitation	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.002)	-0.003 (0.002)
Consumption	6.784** (3.132)	8.773* (4.729)	17.236*** (5.223)	17.710*** (5.428)	7.659 (4.915)
GASPOOL	1.386	1.309	1.227	1.029	2.418

	(2.556)	(2.379)	(1.695)	(1.786)	(2.414)
API2	17.986	14.579	28.363	14.168	10.025
	(15.713)	(14.234)	(17.760)	(14.949)	(14.806)

*, **, and *** indicate significance at a 90%, 95%, and 99% confidence level, respectively. The standard deviation of each regression is presented in parentheses.

For Finland (FI), Denmark (DK1), and Estonia (EE) presented in Table 9(b), the temperature presents two thresholds, which correspond to three regimes, while Denmark (DK2) presents three thresholds. In Finland's first and second regimes, that is, when $temp < -2.96^\circ$ and $-2.96^\circ \leq temp < 12.27^\circ$, the temperature has a negative and significant effect on prices. However, in the second regime, the magnitude of the effect is much smaller. For Denmark in all the regimes, the effect of temperature is negative and significant, yet for the regime that includes zero degrees, the magnitude of the effect is higher than in the other regimes. In the case of Estonia, the regime that includes zero degrees is the one with the highest negative effect of temperature on prices. Regarding the control variables, all of them are significant with the expected signs, except for coal prices that do not have an impact on prices.

Finally, for Norway presented in Table 9(c), the temperature in NO1 and NO2 presents three thresholds (four regimes), while in NO3, NO4, and NO5, it presents only one (two regimes). For all the regimes in the five areas, the relationship between temperature and prices is negative and significant. Moreover, as in the case of the other countries, the highest magnitude of the effect is documented in the regime that includes zero degrees. For example, when the temperature is below 1.30° , in NO1, a decrease in one degree increases electricity prices by almost €2. The control variables wind speed and consumption are statistically significant with the expected signs, while GASPOOL and API2 are not significant, as expected, given the low dependence of Norway on fossil fuels.

6. Discussion

The effect of stopping hydroelectric plants on the dynamics of electricity prices in the Nord Pool day-ahead market is identified. A regression model that uses an indicator variable for the days that freezing events occur is proposed. A freezing event occurs on the days on which the temperature drops below zero degrees Celsius and hydroelectric plants are not able to turbine water any more due to the freezing of water reservoirs. For all the area

prices of the Nord Pool market analyzed, it is found that the average electricity prices increase between €1 and €6 once a freezing event occurs. Before a freezing event, the relationship between prices and temperature is statistically insignificant for all the area prices, except for some areas within Norway. However, once a freezing event occurs, this relationship becomes significant and negative (for each degree that the temperature decreases, prices increase between €1 and €3), indicating that lower temperatures trigger price increments. Even though these factors stand for all area prices, Norway and Sweden face the highest effect of temperature on prices. In other words, for each degree that the temperature drops, these two countries face higher increments in the prices in comparison to the other countries of the market.

These results provide relevant insights about how a higher dependence on hydroelectric production makes Norway and Sweden more vulnerable to temperature, particularly when it drops below zero, and other more expensive technologies, such as thermal plants, must be turned on to meet demand. Nevertheless, the integrated market becomes vulnerable to this supply shock as it may be transmitted to other areas when Norway and Sweden export their surplus of electricity to the other areas of the Nord Pool⁴.

The indicator regression model is extended to include control variables that are also expected to affect the distribution of prices. These variables are weather-related (wind speed and precipitation) and market-related (consumption, natural gas prices, and coal prices). Once these control variables are included in the model setup, the effects of freezing events on prices are marginally less pronounced, but still significant. By adding other renewable sources, such as wind power, the model considers that once hydroelectric plants are no longer available for power generation, not only are more expensive technologies such as thermal plants left for generation, but also, for example, the system can rely on wind power generation, which has a lower marginal cost than thermal plants.

Water reservoirs do not necessary freeze exactly when the empirical temperature measures below zero degrees. The threshold may differ owing to the way the temperature series were

⁴ In 2015, only Norway, Sweden, and Estonia had a surplus of electricity. Norway exported 15 TWh to the other members of the integrated market, Sweden exported 23 TWh, and Estonia only 1 TWh. (<http://www.nordpoolspot.com/>).

constructed and for other physical reasons, such as the level of snowpack that can determine the freezing and unfreezing of water reservoirs. To consider this fact, a threshold regression that endogenously selects the level(s) at which the relationship between electricity prices and temperature changes is also proposed. One to three thresholds for the temperature variable in different areas are found. However, the results found with the indicator variable remain: for the regimes in which zero degrees is included, the effect of temperature on prices is always higher (and significant) than in the other regimes.

While Norway and Sweden at all times face a higher impact of temperature on their area prices, this effect is transmitted to the other area prices as Norway and Sweden are the biggest players in the market, and they present an electricity surplus that is exported to the other countries. However, the results indicate that the diversification of the generation mix by including a higher share of renewable technologies, different from hydropower, soften the effect of freezing events on prices, as is mainly the case in Finland, Denmark, and Estonia. Moreover, a higher integration between the areas of the Nord Pool and other European markets by an expansion of the transmission capacities, may also allow the smoothing effects of wind power generation to be more easily transmitted.

Currently, due to physical interconnection restrictions, it is evident that not all supply shocks, nor all the smoothing that renewables such as wind power generate, are transmitted between areas. These findings not only demonstrate the vulnerabilities of an integrated market as the Nord Pool, but also establish the potential benefits of expanding the market even further. These findings may contribute to the decisions of policy makers in the market related to the expansion of transmission capacities between areas, increments in the incentives for investing in renewable technologies, and for market planning by forecasting the increment in electricity prices once a freezing event occurs. Additionally, to make informed and more accurate decisions, market participants, such as consumers, distributors, and producers of electricity may also base their buying/selling strategies on these findings.

7. Conclusions

The effect of stopping hydroelectric plants on electricity prices in the Nord Pool day-ahead market is assessed. The plants may stop due to the freezing of water reservoirs on extreme cold days. Two approaches are followed to identify the impact of such freezing event: OLS

regression with an indicator variable for the days when the temperature is below zero degrees Celsius; and, threshold regression to select endogenously the temperature at which a freezing event occurs. With both methodologies, it is found that the relationship between prices and temperature is negative once a freezing event occurs. Thus, lower temperatures trigger price increments, given that hydroelectric plants are not generating electricity and more expensive technologies, such as thermal plants, must be turned on to meet demand. As expected, the countries with a higher dependence from hydroelectric generation, like Norway and Sweden, face the highest effect of temperature on prices. While, countries with a more diversified generation mix that have a higher share of renewable technologies, different from hydropower, like Finland, Denmark and Estonia, receive a softer effect of freezing events. Nevertheless, the fact that the Nord Pool is an integrated market, implies that the shocks of halting hydropower generation from the countries most dependent of this generation source are transmitted to the other areas of the Nord Pool. In the same sense, the smoothing effects of wind power generation may be transmitted across countries.

The results found imply that expanding the integrated Nord Pool market, by increasing the interconnection capacities among the current countries and by extending the market to other European countries, have potential benefits as the smoothing effects of other renewables different from hydropower generation may be more easily transmitted. Regarding the limitations of the study, other moments of the distribution of prices different from the mean, like the variance, may be analyzed to provide risk implications for market participants and policy makers. Lastly, future research opportunities lie on extending the study to other markets using the same methodology proposed here. For instance, the analysis may be performed in the electricity market of the United States, where the main source of generation is natural-gas-fired plants. In this case, the event of interest could be wars that affect the supply of natural gas.

Appendix 1. Variables construction summary

Variable	Type	Units	Tickers	Source	Construction
<i>Freezing Events Variables</i>					
Temperature	Weather	Degrees Celsius	WER1SE00 WER1FI00 WER1DN00 WER1NO00 WER1EI00	Bloomberg	Average of the actual temperature of the main cities within the country.
Indicator	Weather	Binary	-	Own elaboration	Takes the value of 1 when the temperature of the country is below 0°, and a value of 0 otherwise.
<i>Control Variables</i>					
Wind Speed	Weather	m/s	WER1SE00 WER1FI00 WER1DN00 WER1NO00 WER1EI00	Bloomberg	Average of the actual wind speed of the main cities within the country.
Precipitation	Weather	Integer in 100th mm	WER1SE00 WER1FI00 WER1DN00 WER1NO00 WER1EI00	Bloomberg	Average of the actual precipitation of the main cities within the country.
Consumption	Market	MWh	-	Nord Pool	Total megawatts hours consumed per area of the Nord Pool.
Natural Gas Price	Market	€/MWh	EEXGSPD	Datastream	GASPOOL Index: natural gas delivered to the GASPOOL market area.
Coal Price	Market	\$/MT	LMCYSPT	Datastream	API2 index : steam coal delivered to the ARA region of Northwest Europe.

Appendix 2. Pearson correlation coefficient between Temperature and Consumption

SE1	SE2	SE3	SE4	FI	DK1	DK2
-0.018	-0.038	-0.040	-0.022	-0.051	-0.004	-0.005
NO1	NO2	NO3	NO4	NO5	EE	
-0.050	-0.054	-0.032	-0.029	-0.047	-0.022	

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Figures

Figure 1. Data structural diagram

Figure 2. Electricity prices (EUR/MWh): January 2013-December 2016

Figure 3. Temperature (degrees Celsius): January 2013-December 2016

Figure 4. Diagram of the proposed methodology

Note: We used Eviews 9 and MATLAB in this study to carried out our calculations.

Figure 5. Plot of the change in the intercept of the regression and in the slope related to temperature after a freezing event occurs

Figure 6. Plot of the change in the intercept of the regression and in the slope related to temperature after a freezing event occurs (with control variables)

